

A COMBINED DIC-PIV EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH FOR THE STUDY OF IMPACT RESPONSE OF WATER-BACKED PANELS

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ABSTRACT

Predicting the response of water-backed structures to impulsive loading is essential to the design of marine and aeronautical structures. Recent laboratory studies have advanced our comprehension of this fluid-structure interaction, by focusing on the archetypal geometry of a flexible plate resting on the water surface. Despite significant progress in experiments and modeling, several technical questions remain open due to the lack of experimental approaches to simultaneously characterize the plate structural response and the water flow physics. The objective of this study is to demonstrate a combined approach to study the impact response of a compliant plate resting on the surface of water. Quantification of the fluid-structure interaction is based on the integration of particle image velocimetry and digital image correlation, two techniques that constitute the gold standard for non-invasive measurement in experimental fluid and solid mechanics, respectively. The proposed experimental framework is used to simultaneously quantify the structural response and the flow physics, thereby shedding light on the fluid-structure interaction.

1 INTRODUCTION

Understanding the dynamic response of water-backed structures to impulsive loading is critical to the design of naval and aeronautical structures. To study the mechanism underlying water-backed impact, past research has focused on the archetypal geometry of a flexible plate resting on the water surface [1]. Prior experiments have helped quantify the influence of the water on the response of several composite plates [2, 3]. These studies have been supported by theoretical [4] and computational [5] efforts aimed at illuminating the influence of the water on the kinetics, kinematics, and damage mechanics of several composite plates.

Despite significant progress in modeling and simulation, limitations in the experimental techniques have challenged the validation of the theoretical and computational framework. Current experimental measurement largely relies on point-wise measurement of the structural formation and the hydrodynamic pressure using sensors [3, 6], which cannot afford a full-field characterization of the plate structural response and the water flow physics. For example, past studies have utilized potential flow theory to capture the time-evolution of the hydrodynamic loading [7, 8], but experimental validation requires the simultaneous, full-field quantification of both the plate deflection and the flow physics, which has never been attempted.

The objective of this study is to demonstrate a combined experimental framework for the study of low-speed impact of water-backed panels through the integration of digital image correlation (DIC) and particle image velocimetry (PIV). The use of DIC is pervasive in the displacement and strain measurements of solid surfaces [9]. For example, in the study of impact problems, DIC has afforded precise quantification of the structural response with high temporal and spatial resolutions [10, 11]. In this work, DIC was utilized to quantify the deflection of the plate to help elucidate the role of water-backing in the structural response.

Planar two-dimensional PIV is widely used as a non-invasive technique for the quantification of the fluid velocity field [12]. Here, PIV was used to quantify the fluid velocity field induced by the dynamic response of the plate. The hydrodynamic pressure was then reconstructed from the velocity field [13] to elucidate the fluid-structure interaction.

In our recent work, we have demonstrated a combined DIC-PIV approach in the measurement of the structural deformation and the flow physics of a flexible plate placed in a steady cross-flow [14]. To the best of our knowledge, a combined DIC-PIV approach has never been employed in the study of the water-backed impact problem. Here, we propose a few improvements to address potential problems that may arise from the highly unsteady nature of the impact. To resolve the transient fluid-structure interaction, acquisitions of DIC and PIV data were controlled simultaneously with a high temporal resolution. In addition, optical interference between DIC and PIV was eliminated by installing light filters on the cameras to selectively record light at different wavelengths. Finally, we adopted an indirect approach for DIC, in which the DIC camera recorded the apparent in-plane movement of the plate from the top, instead of a direct out-of-plane measurement from the side. This helped mitigate the potential influence of water splashes, surface waves, and air ventilation on the quality of the speckle images. A more complete version of this work has been recently accepted for publication [15].

2 EXPERIMENTS

We experimentally investigated the structural response and the flow physics of associated with the low speed impact of a flexible plate. A schematic of the experimental design and analysis is displayed in Fig. 1. Specifically, a highly-compliant plate fabricated with Polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) was clamped at both ends to rest on the surface of water in a transparent tank. The plate had a half-length $L = 9.5$ cm, thickness $h = 1.0$ cm, and width $b = 6.0$ cm. The plate had an effective Young's modulus of $E = 1.58$ MPa and mass density of $\rho = 1.02 \times 10^3$ kg/m³. The depth of water was maintained at 20 cm through all experimental trials.

The impact was realized by the free fall of a cylindrical-shaped impactor from a drop tower. The total mass of the impactor was 231.7 grams. A range of drop heights (H) from 1 cm to 10 cm were examined to elicit a nominal impact speed between 0.45 m/s to 1.41 m/s. Before the start of each experimental trial, the impactor was held at a given height by an electromagnet.

Figure 1. Schematic of the data acquisition and analysis process.

PIV was utilized to quantify the flow physics during the impact. Polyamid particles with diameter of 50 μm were used as seeding particles. A Dantec Dynamics PIV system, consisting of a 532 nm

wavelength continuous wave Nd:YAG laser, a high-speed camera, and a timer box, was used to acquire the time-resolved particle images below the plate. The seeding particles were illuminated on a two-dimensional plane by a laser sheet generated below the plate, and particle images were acquired from the front (Fig. 1). The camera had a field of view of 30.3×22.3 cm and a resolution of 1632×1200 pixels. The acquisition rate of the camera was 1000 Hz and the exposure time was 1000 μ s.

DIC was employed to investigate the dynamic response of the plate. To create a high-contrast speckle pattern, a layer of red silicone paint was first uniformly applied onto the top surface of the plate, and a blue acrylic paint was then sprayed on top of the red paint. A 120 W LED light was utilized as the light source for DIC. The speckle images were recorded via a high-speed camera fixed above the drop tower, with a field of view of 34.0×25.0 cm and a resolution of 1632×1200 pixels. The acquisition rate was 1000 Hz and the exposure time was 500 μ s.

To avoid interference of illumination between PIV and DIC, optical filters were installed on both the cameras and the LED light. The PIV camera was equipped with a band-pass filter with a center wavelength of 532 nm and a bandwidth of 10 nm to allow selective recording at the laser emission wavelength. On the other hand, the DIC camera and the LED light were fitted with red cut-on filters, with cut-on wavelengths of 570 nm and 590 nm, respectively.

The release of the impactor and the onset of camera acquisition were simultaneously triggered. At the start of each trial, a data acquisition board controlled a microcontroller to generate a high voltage signal, which triggered the electromagnet to release the impactor and initiated the acquisition of high-speed images through a trigger box. Exemplary images of the particles and the speckle pattern simultaneously acquired by PIV and DIC are displayed in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Exemplary images of the particles (left) and the speckle pattern (right) simultaneously acquired by PIV and DIC cameras superimposed by our definition of a coordinate system. The white bars are 2 cm in length.

3 ANALYSIS

3.1 DIC analysis

The quantification of the dynamic response of the plate consisted of two steps. First, the apparent in-plane displacement the speckles, caused by the plate deflection, was derived from the speckle images. Using the speckle image before the impact as a reference, the apparent in-plane displacement during the impact was obtained through correlation between the deformed speckle images and the reference image. The correlation was performed in the open source software, Ncorr [16]. The out-of-plane displacement of the plate was then inferred from the apparent in-plane displacement based on a linearized pin-hole camera model [17].

3.2 PIV analysis

The velocity field below the mid-width of the plate was obtained from the particle images using an open source software, PIVlab [18]. Prior to the analysis, a mask was manually created to exclude the plate and clamp from the particle images. Each particle image was partitioned into square interrogation windows of $N \times N$ pixels with a 50% overlap. The flow velocity within each interrogation window was then obtained by cross-correlating particles on consecutive images. In our analysis, three levels of interrogation window sizes, $N = 64, 32,$ and $16,$ were successively used to ensure the accuracy of the

cross-correlation. A Poisson equation-based approach was implemented to reconstruct the pressure field from the velocity field [13].

4 RESULTS

To ease our discussions, we introduce a few characteristic scales to nondimensionalize the physical parameters. A characteristic time scale is defined as $T = \frac{1}{\omega_1}$, with $\omega_1 = \frac{\lambda_1^2 h}{L^2} \sqrt{\frac{E}{12\rho_b}}$ and $\lambda_1 = 2.365$, such that $T = 14.3$ ms. A characteristic pressure is defined as $P = \rho h^2 \omega_1^2 = 486.9$ Pa. A characteristic speed is introduced based on the nominal impact speed, $v_0 = \sqrt{2gH}$, where g is gravity.

4.1 Structural response of the plate

The mid-span deflection of the water-backed plate is displayed in Fig. 3. The time at which the maximum plate deflection was attained, t_{\max}/T , was longer than air-backed impact [15]. The slower dynamics may be attributed to the added mass effect. In agreement with [6], the maximum mid-plate deflection, w_{\max}/h , for water-backed impact was smaller than air-backed impact. However, our finding is in contrast to [19], in which water-backing was found to enhance deformation of composite plates. The surprising findings may be attributed to material damages induced by the impact, which could reduce the sample stiffness [3] and lead to larger deformation.

Figure 3. Plate deflection at the mid-span for water-backed impact at various drop heights.

4.2 Flow physics

The velocity and pressure fields below the plate were examined to elucidate the flow physics. Figure 4 displays the velocity fields for drop heights $H = 1$ cm and $H = 10$ cm at two time instants during the impact. At the onset of the impact, a localized high velocity region can be observed under the mid-span of the plate (Fig. 4(a) and (b)). As the plate deformed further, the fluid velocity magnitude became smaller (Fig. 4(c) and (d)).

The role of the water during the impact was further quantified from the hydrodynamic loading on the plate. Figure 5 displays the pressure fields associated with the velocity fields in Fig. 4. As expected, larger drop heights induced higher hydrodynamic loading below the mid-span at the onset of the impact. In addition, a high pressure region can be observed below the mid-span of the plate (Fig. 5(a) and (b)), which was likely caused by the high acceleration of the plate. As the plate decelerated, the hydrodynamic pressure decreased (Fig. 5(c) and (d)). For large drop heights ($H = 5$ cm and 10 cm), a negative pressure was observed to develop below the mid-span of the plate at the later stage of the impact (Fig. 5(d)), which could have attributed to the onset of air ventilations observed during the experimental trials.

Figure 4. Velocity field measured by PIV for drop heights (a,c) $H = 1$ cm and (b,d) $H = 10$ cm. The time instants correspond to (a,b) $t = 0.1t_{\max}$ and (c) $t = t_{\max}$. The velocity field in (d) is shown at the last time instant before air ventilation. The contour curves represent the velocity magnitude and the arrows represent velocity direction. Gray areas represent masks for the plate and the clamp.

Figure 5. Contour plots of the pressure fields associated with the velocity fields displayed in Fig. 4.

To elucidate the interaction between the plate and water, in Fig. 6, we display the profiles of the plate deflection and the hydrodynamic loading at a series of time instants during the impact for drop height $H = 10$ cm. At all time instants during the impact, the maximum deflection of the plate was located around the mid-span, and the deflection profiles resembled the fundamental mode shape (Fig. 6(a)). In contrast, the hydrodynamic loading profile could not be captured with a single mode. At the onset of the impact, a localized pressure peak was observed below the mid-span of the plate. During the impact, this localized high pressure region traveled back and forth along the span of the plate as the pressure peak slowly diffused (Fig. 6(b)).

Figure 6. Profiles of the plate deflection and the hydrodynamic loading on the plate at a series of time instants for drop height $H = 10$ cm.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we demonstrated a combined DIC-PIV approach for the simultaneous measurement of the structural response and the flow physics associated with the impact of a water-backed panel. DIC measurement of the structural response of water-backed panels helped elucidate the role of water-backing on the structural response. PIV measurement of the flow velocity demonstrated a localized high velocity region below the mid-span of the plate, while the hydrodynamic loading on the plate revealed a rich temporal evolution during the impact. The proposed experimental can help advance our understanding of highly unsteady fluid-structure interactions associated with water-backed impact.

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